

Circle packing inside a regular decagon: supplemental material

Paolo Amore

Facultad de Ciencias, CUICBAS, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
paolo@ucol.mx

January 26, 2023

Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular decagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular decagon obtained using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that the configurations that we have reached correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, we believe that they should provide good lower bounds. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader is advised to refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular decagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular decagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.487457184532	0.508000488876	41	0.134256277432	0.789976627244
3	0.44667227211	0.639823850885	42	0.133318962162	0.797984253966
4	0.399888622321	0.683753039327	43	0.13106913537	0.789642486993
5	0.363271264003	0.705331496239	44	0.129604642532	0.790050726297
6	0.327711741621	0.688805232454	45	0.128459831467	0.793795061459
7	0.318272363712	0.757978840384	46	0.126798956611	0.790588284768
8	0.291381365584	0.726063690358	47	0.125313691129	0.788961999305
9	0.267080810777	0.686260598058	48	0.124153849577	0.790902230881
10	0.253797712807	0.688551757271	49	0.122928467615	0.791520557417
11	0.245912809724	0.711076247882	50	0.122031074191	0.795924834532
12	0.239508524406	0.735841672468	51	0.120583478944	0.792696568474
13	0.233234508668	0.755944916408	52	0.11964847229	0.795754021783
14	0.22717617332	0.772351115786	53	0.118820526155	0.799871080368
15	0.217430954421	0.758045347389	54	0.117454379954	0.796330547992
16	0.209167036152	0.748286053443	55	0.116838386231	0.802592269468
17	0.202348453391	0.744063298307	56	0.115350009573	0.796497615305
18	0.197916840583	0.753701166192	57	0.11460938489	0.800343462991
19	0.19674245906	0.786160057086	58	0.113393216654	0.797192725503
20	0.188578704372	0.76028509057	59	0.112620123311	0.79991748839
21	0.184347905722	0.762881167739	60	0.111611453279	0.798969056234
22	0.178203275655	0.746818778253	61	0.110697111541	0.799030938854
23	0.175298553497	0.755519510467	62	0.10961976555	0.796398824508
24	0.172069669621	0.759593210954	63	0.108790842219	0.797051549402
25	0.168694134478	0.760503393793	64	0.107944231889	0.797149976601
26	0.166892314386	0.774118070814	65	0.107090797303	0.796854158853
27	0.163673253308	0.773179582538	66	0.106597558144	0.801677382682
28	0.160493896012	0.770967824967	67	0.105861389913	0.802622202722
29	0.157972155276	0.773606780941	68	0.105339317195	0.806586768961
30	0.156362761908	0.784059648849	69	0.104672588057	0.808120638843
31	0.15285899604	0.774292196963	70	0.104183749852	0.812192907495
32	0.150803659853	0.777919977294	71	0.102867938151	0.803118447936
33	0.148349698972	0.77633374074	72	0.102386101047	0.806818205813
34	0.146024252954	0.774979271162	73	0.101412253308	0.802536711911
35	0.144665798604	0.782998563102	74	0.100703278809	0.802195321588
36	0.143055643571	0.78754191035	75	0.0999731744815	0.801289425954
37	0.141569957672	0.792693161442	76	0.0995583344117	0.805248677155
38	0.139018002886	0.785031114233	77	0.0987392198997	0.802474593865
39	0.137467724844	0.787820504577	78	0.0982656387513	0.805117281693
40	0.135576893097	0.785945676145	79	0.0977575912259	0.80702921757

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular decagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0970862828576	0.806059159197	121	0.0795652960159	0.818830326778
81	0.0964630721578	0.80569075516	122	0.0793151428712	0.820414326192
82	0.0960999527777	0.809508445347	123	0.0789841702267	0.820250331356
83	0.095739817606	0.813250739723	124	0.0785243341902	0.817318621058
84	0.0950966126435	0.812027176591	125	0.0781937320408	0.816986874733
85	0.0947417954577	0.815573921346	126	0.0779334533377	0.818049474272
86	0.0942893775	0.817306911209	127	0.0776954754569	0.819513970291
87	0.0934098414525	0.811457363468	128	0.0774312294206	0.820358084659
88	0.0929003616351	0.811855363874	129	0.0771306403292	0.820360548975
89	0.0924398793829	0.812961408439	130	0.0768072597416	0.819802196199
90	0.0917547037097	0.809954022871	131	0.0765165010773	0.819865636147
91	0.0915160745343	0.81469929794	132	0.0763273263647	0.822044284553
92	0.0909145460751	0.812860012912	133	0.0760851281289	0.823023766729
93	0.0904356810129	0.813062176558	134	0.0757149411967	0.821162598277
94	0.0898438900401	0.811084555897	135	0.0754213141614	0.820886554592
95	0.0893795269103	0.811261547374	136	0.0751352125597	0.820705096181
96	0.0888831054188	0.81071994123	137	0.0749164388848	0.821932211308
97	0.0884616659277	0.811415211279	138	0.0745706003154	0.820305357668
98	0.0879339440744	0.810028621534	139	0.0743349404473	0.821035582043
99	0.0875624922473	0.811395520998	140	0.0740892107803	0.82148408847
100	0.0871061092095	0.811070141914	141	0.0738624772915	0.822295729211
101	0.0867956425993	0.813351744571	142	0.0735160800321	0.820378388728
102	0.0864435437366	0.814753959335	143	0.0732434572128	0.820039725516
103	0.0861036931806	0.816285284188	144	0.0730566848484	0.821568155049
104	0.0857885307517	0.818187767783	145	0.0727507893727	0.820360243222
105	0.0851752007314	0.814285710444	146	0.0727133512215	0.825167967687
106	0.0847452082477	0.813761896809	147	0.0724092577966	0.823885215694
107	0.0843133603402	0.813088386462	148	0.0722672349511	0.826239160642
108	0.0838574780401	0.811836424502	149	0.0720374594615	0.826540669877
109	0.0835992208742	0.81431444898	150	0.0718521733954	0.827813035024
110	0.0832567103836	0.815065221849	151	0.0717355109935	0.830627915923
111	0.0830240009631	0.817883559915	152	0.0715144175095	0.830982699698
112	0.0827216825061	0.819252780363	153	0.0712660188497	0.830649122547
113	0.0824678220728	0.821502098279	154	0.07114666199	0.83328000695
114	0.0821675075867	0.822746913173	155	0.0708234604944	0.831088297551
115	0.0816895259799	0.820336008763	156	0.0706977682082	0.833483851213
116	0.0813949921496	0.821513195258	157	0.0702857734237	0.829078574095
117	0.0809207369716	0.818967567991	158	0.0699462253755	0.826317281867
118	0.080644477191	0.820337286664	159	0.0696375276424	0.824223504308
119	0.0802305515282	0.81881860081	160	0.0694110468973	0.824021143137
120	0.0799233134988	0.819387606206	161	0.0692729711075	0.825875701714

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular decagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0689161980104	0.822467636715	182	0.0651462684424	0.825679800424
163	0.0688005134621	0.824768652888	183	0.0650932169391	0.828864888758
164	0.0684991326601	0.822574374784	184	0.0648660676528	0.827587928841
165	0.0683549184501	0.824109017552	185	0.0646715768077	0.827103410017
166	0.0681962305982	0.825258511705	186	0.0644977988789	0.827111224693
167	0.0681313500343	0.828650970819	187	0.0643530905965	0.827830851494
168	0.0679790572106	0.8298903967	188	0.0642397783733	0.829329473923
169	0.0677925173784	0.830254828325	189	0.0640365903727	0.828474960398
170	0.0676192973927	0.830905076146	190	0.064015015931	0.832297326944
171	0.0673222903454	0.828466703315	191	0.0637764691462	0.830453832731
172	0.0672900824988	0.832514394724	192	0.0635918911492	0.829976685445
173	0.0670136793428	0.830489627578	193	0.063504792261	0.832015642541
174	0.0667611109038	0.829005746089	194	0.063429367487	0.834341170472
175	0.0666292568847	0.830479986506	195	0.0633228661016	0.835828011029
176	0.0664326709391	0.830304283167	196	0.0631580619216	0.835747033713
177	0.0661754544769	0.828568301793	197	0.0629688985899	0.834986787014
178	0.066036422166	0.829751900738	198	0.0628443798967	0.835909505648
179	0.0658507154242	0.829726974607	199	0.0626116178478	0.833919465176
180	0.0656434836613	0.829119118665	200	0.0624396991622	0.833513777021
181	0.065380165237	0.827050037417			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular decagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

Acknowledgements

The research of P.A. was supported by Sistema Nacional de Investigadores (México).

References

- [1] Amore, Paolo. "Circle packing in regular polygons." arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.12287 (2022).
- [2] Paolo Amore, "Coordinates of the packing configurations of arXiv:2212.12287 ", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574070>